

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_3_6	
Title	Anatrack Mapper (various versions).
Category	Environmental/Spatial
Purpose of the method	Intuitive mapping of areas (e.g. habitats), lines (e.g. routes) and point locations on desktops, laptops, tablets and smartphones by local people, in multiple languages and simple enough to be used by children.
Effort in time	Proficient use in minutes. Original tool was rated 4-5/5 for ease of use.
Number of objects investigated	No limit
Data format	Inputs: own images, tiles from GoogleEarth or OpenStreetmap). Outputs: geospatial data as shapefiles, GeoJSON, KML and CSV but can also create images for presentations and publications.
Description	Coordinates are plotted freehand, or with snap to previous vertices, over maps (e.g. Google Earth) to align them with map coordinates or using walk-round with GPS. Original enabled mapping in 14 EU languages (plus Japanese, Russian, Turkish & Ukrainian) (using CSV upload of translation on Excel sheets). A version is incorporated in the Reciprocal Environmental Decision Support (REDS) system being tested for the Community Sustainability Platform of Pro-Coast. This tool was used for most projects in Chapters 9-19 of Kenward et al. (2013).
Basic Literature	Kenward, R.E., Papathanasiou, J., Arampatzis, E. & Manos, B.A. (eds) (2013). Transactional Environmental Support System Design: Global Solutions. IGI-Global, Hershey, Pennsylvania, USA. https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-2824-3 Tool used for most projects in Chapters 9-19.
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Linked material	To be applied in Arne Parish (CS6) as described now at: https://pro-coast.sycl.net/10/pro-coast-case-studies and (to be developed) at: https://pro-coast-uk.sycl.net/ and for sites in at least 11 other languages as part of the Pro-Coast Community Sustainability Platform.